

INTERDISCIPLINARY EFFECTS BETWEEN DISCIPLINE, CULTURE AND LANGUAGE. ALTERATIONS WITHIN CULTURE AND LANGUAGE IN THE GLOBALIZATION PROCESS

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Abstract. This article analyzes the influence of globalization on language and culture. Special attention is given to the growing use of English in young people's speech, the rise of bilingual communication, and the integration of foreign words into daily life. A survey was conducted among 13 participants to investigate this issue. The findings show that globalization has a significant impact on language changes in modern society.

Keywords: globalization, language change, cultural influence, English language, communication, bilingualism, social media, youth language.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada globalizatsiya jarayonining til va madaniyatga ta'siri tahlil qilinadi. Xususan, yoshlar nutqida ingliz tilining keng qo'llanilishi, kundalik hayotda ikki tillilikning kuchayishi hamda xorijiy so'zlarning kirib kelishi o'rganildi. Tadqiqot davomida 13 nafar ishtirokchi o'rtasida so'rovnomma o'tkazildi. Natijalar globalizatsiya til o'zgarishlariga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatayotganini ko'rsatdi.

Kalit so'zlar: globalizatsiya, til, madaniyat, ingliz tili, kommunikatsiya, yoshlar.

Аннотация. В данной статье анализируется влияние глобализации на язык и культуру. Особое внимание уделяется широкому использованию английского языка в речи молодежи, усилению двуязычия в повседневной жизни и проникновению иностранных слов. В ходе исследования был проведен опрос среди 13 участников. Результаты показали, что глобализация оказывает значительное влияние на языковые изменения.

Ключевые слова: глобализация, язык, культура, английский язык, коммуникация, молодежь.

The world is changing quickly because of globalization. Globalization means that countries and people are becoming more connected through the internet, education, trade, media, and communication. As a result, the way people speak and the values they have are changing a lot. English is becoming a global language that is used for communication between different countries. Today, students and teenagers often use English words when they speak their native language. Social media, movies, music, and the internet have a strong influence on this process.

Globalization allows people to communicate with others from different parts of the world and makes it easier to learn foreign languages. At the same time, it can also influence local languages and cultural traditions.

The purpose of this article is to examine how globalization influences language use and cultural identity in today's world (Crystal, 2003; UNESCO, 2010).

In this study, a survey was conducted among students who are my groupmates to collect information about their language use. A total of 13 participants answered questions related to the languages they use in their daily lives. The survey questions included:

- the language participants use every day;
- how often they use English words while speaking;
- and where they learn English words.

After collecting the responses, the data were analyzed using percentages and simple comparison methods. This helped identify the influence of globalization on the way young people communicate.

The findings show that globalization has a significant influence on language use. Most participants (69.2%) stated that they use both Uzbek and English in daily communication. Meanwhile, 30.8% mainly use Uzbek, and only a small number primarily use English.

Question	Main Result	Percentage
 Language used in daily life	Both Uzbek and English	69.2%
	Only Uzbek	30.8%
	Only English	7.7%
 Use of English words in speech	Often	58.3%
	Sometimes	33.3%
	Never	8.3%
 Source of foreign words	Social media	63.6%
	Movies and music	45.5%
	School	27.3%

Admittedly, social media was identified as one of the main sources for learning English vocabulary. Approximately 63.6% of participants learn English words by social media. Others voted for learning from movies and music (45.5%), while some learn them at school (27.3%).

These findings illustrate that globalization and digital communication are changing the way young people interact and communicate with one another.

The study shows that globalization has both positive and negative effects on language and culture. One positive effect is that people could communicate with individuals from different countries and improve their foreign language skills. English also provides students with easily access to information, education, and future career opportunities

Social media and entertainment also play an important role in spreading English vocabulary. Since young people spend a considerable amount of time online, they naturally learn and use English expressions in their everyday communication. According to studies on language learning and digital media use, frequent exposure to online content significantly increases the use of foreign vocabulary among young users (Crystal, 2019).

However, globalization may also reduce the use of native languages. If people increasingly rely on English words and expressions, some traditional language forms and cultural values may gradually disappear. This process can have an impact on national identity and cultural heritage.

Language is an essential part of culture because it carries traditions, history, and social values. Therefore, while learning foreign languages, people should also respect and preserve their native language and cultural traditions.

In conclusion, globalization has a strong influence on language and culture in today's world. The study shows that many young people use both Uzbek and English in their daily communication because of the impact of social media and entertainment. Globalization creates many opportunities for communication, education, and cultural exchange between people from different countries. It allows individuals to share ideas, learn new languages, and understand different cultures more easily. At the same time, it is important to protect native languages and cultural traditions, as they are an important part of national identity.

Finding a balance between global communication and maintaining national identity is essential for the future development of societies. While globalization brings many benefits, it can also lead to the gradual loss of local language use if it is not properly managed. Therefore, both global integration and cultural preservation should be considered equally important.

Further studies involving a larger number of participants may provide a deeper and more accurate understanding of this topic and its long-term effects on language and culture

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